

Project Management Handbook

Deliverable 1.1 Project Management Handbook

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Description

Internal guide stating the procedures and rules on project management (contacts, financial data, project KPIs, templates, guides) for project quality assurance.

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Disclaimer:

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Abstract:

The present document is the EmpoWomen “Project Management Handbook”. The Project Management Handbook describes the project organisation and management, collaboration and information sharing procedures, and reporting and quality assurance mechanisms. The handbook aims to support all consortium partners and facilitate the day-to-day work and project activities. The handbook complements the established and in force Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA).

List of Acronyms

Version	Submission date
CA	Consortium Agreement
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
CW	Collaborative Workspace
DoA	Description of Action
DR	Deliverable Responsible
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GMS	Grant Management System
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
GA	General Assembly
TL	Task Leader
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive Summary

The present document is deliverable D1.1 – “Project Management Handbook”, framed within the EU-required WP1 – “Coordination and Management” of the EmpoWomen project. The main objective of project management within the EmpoWomen project is to establish a common vision and understanding of the project and how it should be carried out over its 24-month duration.

The Project Management Handbook describes the project organisation and management, collaboration and information sharing procedures, and reporting and quality assurance mechanisms. The handbook aims to support all consortium partners and facilitate the day-to-day work and project activities. The handbook complements the established and in force Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA), which take primacy when there is any conflicting information with what is included in the handbook.

EmpoWomen organisation and management structure

The EmpoWomen consortium consists of four partners from four European countries (Spain, Ukraine, Belgium and Estonia). With a primary focus on fostering women leadership, entrepreneurship, and investment in startup ecosystems, the consortium boasts a strategic alliance with eight associated partners from Latvia, Slovakia, the Canary Islands in Spain, Georgia, Croatia, Tunisia, Moldova, and Bulgaria.

These associated partners, strategically selected for their geographical location, extensive outreach, established networks, and expertise, are poised to serve as effective ambassadors, expanding the project's reach across targeted countries. The consortium's size and composition ensure a balanced and fair distribution, enabling EmpoWomen to engage startups from EU-widening countries through its open calls.

The consortium's creation is driven by specific goals, including expertise in designing and implementing acceleration programs for female entrepreneurship, knowledge of deep-tech technologies, proficiency in coaching women entrepreneurs, and a robust market position in building startup ecosystems. Furthermore, the consortium brings deep expertise in acceleration programs for pre-revenue and seed companies, a network of investors with remarkable exits, and financial viability to effectively manage substantial project funds.

Shifting the focus to the project's management structure, EmpoWomen has established a streamlined approach to enhance efficiency and clarify responsibilities. Key components include the Project Coordinator (SPLORO), the Project Management Board as the decision-making body, and Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders, and an external ethics advisor providing crucial support to ensure the project's success.

Collaboration, information, and knowledge management

The EmpoWomen project has adopted a private collaborative workspace to facilitate the collaboration between partners and the sharing of information and knowledge. The workspace supports information exchange and collaborative work on documents, the management of information gathered and developed within the framework of the project, and provides a coordination, planning and project monitoring tool.

An integral part of the collaborative workspace is the EmpoWomen Mastersheet, a shared document that is the transposition of all relevant information from the GA (particularly the DoA) into an easy-to-access and editable document. The Mastersheet includes specific information about the project, including the work packages, the project Gantt chart, the list of deliverables and milestones, KPIs, among many others. It is accessible and editable by all partners, thus ensuring the collaborative spirit of the project.

Project reporting

Project reporting encompasses several types of reports that will be expected throughout the project. These include internal reports, to be developed with contributions of all partners every six months; report for the EC (final and financial report), due at M24; and timesheets.

Quality assurance

The establishment of quality assurance mechanisms aim to ensure a high quality of project deliverables and other project management procedures. While the Project Coordinator is the main responsible for quality assurance, all partners participate in ensuring quality in the work they deliver.

Regarding documents, and particularly official deliverables, specific rules have been defined to ensure these are consistent and developed with quality. For this purpose, different templates have been prepared and an internal review timeline has been defined.

Also related to quality assurance is risk management, which addresses those risks that could jeopardise the project meeting its objectives and delivery the planned results. Risk analysis is a consortium-wide effort and managed collaboratively with the support of the EmpoWomen Mastersheet. Potential risks will be analysed on a regular basis to identify the emergence of risks as early as possible and define the optimal mitigation approach.

Dissemination and communication processes

Dissemination and communication efforts are essential for the success of EmpoWomen by promoting the project's objectives, activities, and achievements. All partners have efforts in driving dissemination and communication.

Dissemination and communication are driven through the strategy outlined in the EmpoWomen D&C Plan. Several KPIs specifically addressing Dissemination and Communication activities have been defined and to which all partners must contribute.

To support the defined strategy, several pillars have been set up, including a Communication & Dissemination tracker (focused on publications, and events), and a stakeholder database.

1. Introduction

The present document is deliverable D1.1 – “Project Management Handbook”, framed within the EU-required WP1 - “Coordination and Management” of the EmpoWomen project.

The main objective of project management within the EmpoWomen project is to establish a common vision and understanding the project and how it should be carried out over its 24-month duration. This implies that all partners are continuously aware of their own work and the work done by other partners.

Furthermore, the Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for managing the administrative requirements associated with the contractual obligations with the European Commission (EC), as well as implementing quality control procedures that ensure quality outputs of the project activities supported on a rigorous quality review of the project deliverables, regular assessment of EmpoWomen progress and achievements, and the proper management of risks. The structures and procedures that have been implemented and the quality control procedures have been designed to achieve these objectives.

The day-to-day management of the project includes, among others, management of documentation, reporting, organisation of meetings, set-up and management of the communication structure, maintenance of an information and documentation repository, and management of knowledge and IPR within the consortium.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The EmpoWomen Project Management Handbook describes the project organisation and management, collaboration and information sharing procedures, and reporting and quality assurance mechanisms. The handbook aims to support all consortium partners and to facilitate the day-to-day work and project activities, ensuring that efficient collaboration is in place and that all the EC requirements are fulfilled.

The handbook is a living document and will be subject to updates as required over the course of the project. Partners will be informed of any updates to the document.

This handbook complements the established and *in force* Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA). Furthermore, the information contained within the GA and CA must always take primacy when there is any conflicting information with what is included in the handbook.

1.2 Deliverable structure

The deliverable is structured into the following sections:

- **Introduction**, the current section.
- **About EmpoWomen** provides relevant information about the project, such as its objectives, duration, and budget.
- **EmpoWomen organisation and management** addresses the different management structures of the project.
- **Collaboration, information, and knowledge management** focuses on the different structures and tools that have been implemented to ensure an efficient collaboration among partners, exchange of information and knowledge.
- **Project reporting** addresses the various reports that will be developed within the course of the project.
- **Project processes** covers various key areas in project management, including risk management, issue management, quality assurance with specific processes for documents, and dissemination and communication processes. It also introduces tools such as a Communication & Dissemination tracker, an Editorial Calendar, and a Stakeholders database.
- **Project closing** proposes a reflection on what to focus on when the project comes to an end.

2. About EmpoWomen

EmpoWomen, operating within the framework of the HORIZON-CSA action and falling under the call designation HORIZON-EIC-2022-STARTUPEU-01, is a project funded by the European Commission under grant agreement number 101120693. This initiative is dedicated to supporting startups led by women in Europe, providing equity-free funding and vouchers for mentorship, business angel investment, and participation in tech summits. The primary goal of EmpoWomen is to promote gender equality and diversity in entrepreneurship, contributing to economic growth and innovation in Europe.

2.1 Objective

The objective of the EmpoWomen project is to support female-led startups in Europe by providing them with the necessary resources and tools to develop their businesses. The project aims to promote gender equality and diversity in entrepreneurship and to contribute to economic growth and innovation in Europe.

2.2 Duration

The EmpoWomen project has a duration of 24 months, starting on 1st November 2023 and ending on 31st October 2025.

2.3 Budget

EmpoWomen project budget is €2.000.000 being 100% funded by the EC. The amount devoted to startups is exactly 75% of the budget (1.5M€) which is divided in:

Table 1. Budget allocated for FSTP

	MAX. GRANT	Nº STARTUPS	TOTAL AMOUNT
Equity-free cash	45,000 €	25	1,125,000 €
Vouchers	12,400 €	25	310,000 €
Prize#1 - Winners	15,000 €	2	30,000 €
Prize#2 - 2nd Place	11,500 €	2	23,000 €
Prize#3 - 3rd Place	6,000 €	2	12,000 €
		TOTAL	1,500,000 €

2.4 Success factors

The success of the EmpoWomen project will be measured by the number of female-led startups that receive funding and vouchers, the number of startups that successfully complete the mentorship and business angel investment programmes, and the number of startups that attend tech summits. The project will also be evaluated based on the impact it has on promoting gender equality and diversity in entrepreneurship and on contributing to economic growth and innovation in Europe.

2.5 Project stakeholders

Engaging with associated partners from Bulgaria, Canarias, Croatia, Latvia, Moldova, Slovakia, Tunisia, and Georgia, the project aims to collaborate with essential ecosystem stakeholders, including local incubators, accelerators, business support organizations, startup associations, National Contact Points (NCPs), and larger European associations and networks. This collaboration will be facilitated through a targeted communication campaign to enhance connectivity between EIC-supported companies and various European Startup Ecosystems. The primary goal is to foster closer ties between the EIC community and diverse local and EU ecosystems, promoting gender equality and diversity in entrepreneurship.

3. EmpoWomen organisation and management structure

The EmpoWomen project has established a lean yet efficient organisation and management structure to ensure the project’s effectiveness and delivery of results. This section addresses the defined structures and the communication flows.

3.1 The EmpoWomen consortium

The EmpoWomen consortium consists of four partners from four European countries (Spain, Ukraine, Belgium, and Estonia). It has been established to bring to the project a valuable background in methodologies and tools relevant to the project, and to incorporate several relevant areas of expertise:

The expertise and value of each partner as well as their involvement in the implementation of the project are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2. EmpoWomen partners, their value and role in the project

Partner	Value for EmpoWomen	Role in the project
SPLORO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SME focused in providing innovation strategy services for a range of organisations. • Founding team working in EU projects during the past 13 years and +20 in innovation services provision. • During the past years working with over +500 startups in the EU through different cascade-funding managed programmes. • Expertise in coordinating innovation programs and funds, with a focus on open calls for women-led startups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination and leadership in Work Package 1 (WP1), which encompasses project coordination, administrative, legal, and financial office functions, as well as the management of funds to partners and third parties, along with the preparation of the Data Management Plan. • Coordination and leadership in Work Package 2 (WP2), execution of calls, scouting applicants, and participation in startup monitoring. • Provider of the online platform for application and evaluation: www.cascadefunding.sploro.eu • Contributor to the definition of the open calls, given their background and experience in such activities. • Engaged in WP4 contributing to dissemination and communication actions.
TECHUA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proficiency in communication, dissemination, and connections with fast-growing ecosystems, especially Ukrainian startups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for designing and executing the project’s Communication and Dissemination strategy (WP4 leader). • Connection with the widening ecosystems, especially with UA startups. • Participation in identification, scouting and assessment of startups to participate in the Open Calls.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in selection process
BAE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialization in investment readiness training. • Connections with European Business Angels • Facilitation of investor matchmaking. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investment readiness trainings. • Connection with European BAs and their associations. • Matchmaking with Investors • Links with the WeGate initiative
SWG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outstanding in leading acceleration programs for women-led startups. • Experience in gender diversity programs. • Connections with investors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceleration programme for women-led startups leading WP3. • Share previous experience of executing programs with general diversity with EIT and other projects. • Mentor network with experts in deep tech. • Connections with a large portfolio of VCs and investing themselves.
ASSOCIATED PARTNERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key contribution in identifying and evaluating startups, as well as in communication, dissemination, and awareness activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification, scouting and assessment of startups to participate in the Open Calls. • Communication, dissemination, and awareness raising activities.

3.2 Management structure and roles

As mentioned, EmpoWomen has established a simple management structure (*in section 4.2, a detailed exposition is provided on the subject matter related to meetings*) to maximise efficiency and limit ambiguity in responsibilities (which is also facilitated by the reduced number of partners):

- The **Project Coordinator (PC)** is responsible for the overall project and administrative management of the EmpoWomen project. SPLORO is the Project Coordinator.
- The **General Assembly** is the decision-making body of the consortium and deals with all key strategic project decisions, while it coordinates and manages items affecting the contractual terms with the EC. The General Assembly shall consist of one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as “Member”).
- The **Work Package Leader (WPL)** is responsible for the technical coordination of the activities of all partners involved in the WP.
- The **Task Leader (TL)** is responsible for the technical coordination of the activities of all partners involved in a specific task of a WP.

Figure 1. EmpoWomen organisational structure

3.2.1 Project Coordinator (Coordination team)

The PC is responsible for the overall coordination of the project and the monitoring of the activities led by other EmpoWomen partners. Acting as PC for SPORO is María Elena Martínez.

More specifically, the PC is responsible for:

- Coordinating the implementation of the project activities, as defined in the Description of Action (DoA). This is to be done by monitoring project progress, identifying difficulties and risks, suggesting corrective actions to partners, and updating the work plan (following proper procedures in agreement with the European Commission).
- Ensuring the fulfilment of the contractual aspects of the project, namely the Grant Agreement (GA), Consortium Agreement (CA), and administrative responsibilities towards the EC, particularly through the project's designated Project Officer (PO).
- Organising and managing the delivery of the official periodic reports to the EC.
- Organising and managing the official project reviews, in coordination with the PO.
- Providing a final check of project deliverables and submitting them to the EC via the designated platform.
- Preparing and chairing project meetings, taking meeting minutes and delivering them to the partners for approval.

As PC, SPORO is also responsible for the financial coordination of the project. Acting as the main financial representative of SPORO is Alberto Sierra. Financial coordination encompasses the following actions:

- Implementing internal financial checks.

- Implementing accounting procedures according to EC standards.
- Implementing effective accounting and monitoring of partner cost statements.

3.2.2 Project General Assembly

The General Assembly is the main decision-making body of the consortium and project and consists of one representative of each partner. Given its composition, the General Assembly contributes to the monitoring of the effective and efficient implementation of the project.

The PC leads the General Assembly and chairs all General Assembly meetings.

The General Assembly is responsible for all decisions that may have an impact on the GA and the CA, and other key decisions that can affect the successful implementation of the project, such as:

- Decisions affecting multiple partners, such as contractual matters, planning, financial matters, major technical decisions, preparation of reporting.
- Major changes in the nature of the project.
- Expenditures not planned in the initially agreed budget.
- Issues concerning the ownership of the results and access rights of the results.

Table 3. EmpoWomen General Assembly

General Assembly	Member
SPLORO	María Elena Martínez
SWG	Alona Belinska
BAE	Reginald Vossen
TECHUA	Natalia Vieriemieieva

3.2.3 Work Package Leaders (WPL)

The Work Package Leaders (WPLs) oversee the technical coordination of activities within their designated Work Package (WP). Serving as the liaison between the partners involved in the respective WP and the Project Coordinator (PC), WPLs are tasked with overseeing the punctual execution and fulfillment of associated deliverables within their WP, ensuring the attainment of WP objectives.

WPLs are expected to provide regular internal reports to the PC, control the quality and the schedule of the work developed, and to actively participate in meetings. WP leaders are also expected to maintain an organised archive of the work developed within their work package, including any results achieved.

To ensure an efficient management of the WP activities, WPL are encouraged to regularly communicate with WP partners through emails and other defined collaboration tools.

Each WP has an appointed WP leader who is responsible for coordinating the scientific / technical activities within their WP (**¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**4). The WP leaders are in contact with the task leaders and partners involved in the WP.

Table 4. EmpoWomen WPs and respective WP leaders

WP	Organisation	WP leader
WP1	SPLORO	María Elena Martínez
WP2	SPLORO	María Elena Martínez
WP3	SWG	Alona Belinska
WP4	TECHUA	Tatiana Morozova

3.2.4 Task Leaders (TL)

The Task Leader (TL) is responsible for the technical coordination of the activities of all partners involved in a specific task of a WP. The Task Leader coordinates the delivery of the objectives of the Task and regularly informs the WPL about the development and progress.

The Task Leader must work closely with the collaborators contributing to each task in the preparation and delivery of task-specific deliverables, as well as providing updates to be included in internal reports and official periodic reports.

3.3 Contractual Management

The primary aim of contractual management is to ensure strict adherence to the stipulations outlined in the Grant Agreement, guaranteeing the provision of requisite services and products that align with the project's expectations.

Specifically, contract management addresses the following situations:

1. Alterations in the composition of the consortium, including the addition or withdrawal of beneficiaries or third parties.
2. Modifications to the technical scope of the project that impact the Description of Action.
3. Adjustments to the Consortium Agreement.
4. Finalizing the contract.

Decisions concerning contractual alterations are made during the General Assembly, in line with the procedures delineated within the CA and Article 39 of the Grant Agreement (except in the case of a change of coordinator). The General Assembly also retains the authority to propose changes to its own framework. Any proposed adjustments to the project's plan and scope must undergo comprehensive review and approval at all levels of project management before being presented to the GA. Any modifications that fail to receive approval at any of these levels will be considered rejected.

The responsibility of processing and coordinating any amendments on behalf of the consortium falls to the Project Coordinator. Furthermore, the Project Coordinator bears the responsibility of incorporating any contractual changes into the project plan.

3.4 Ethics Self-Assessment

The EmpoWomen is not a research project in the strict sense. Regarding ethical aspects of the proposal, the EmpoWomen is subject to the Horizon Europe Ethics Review Procedure's Ethics Screening process. At all times throughout the project the consortium will remain fully aware of, and compliant with, the ethical and legal principles and requirements of European Union policy¹.

¹ European Union policy: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/index.cfm?pg=policy&lib=ethics>

4. Collaboration, information, and knowledge management

4.1 Collaborative workspace (CW)

EmpoWomen uses a private collaborative workspace (CW) to facilitate the collaboration between partners and the sharing of information and knowledge. The access to this workspace is limited to those working within EmpoWomen. Partners are expected to use the CW as a:

- Virtual workspace that facilitates information exchange and collaborative work on documents, namely internal reports, project deliverables, and official periodic reports, thus limiting the number of documents sent via e-mail.
- Living repository for all information gathered and developed within the framework of the project.
- Coordination, planning and project monitoring tool.

WPL, TL and all partners are free to and encouraged to use the CW as necessary to optimise their work and the sharing of information. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** is a screenshot of the main page of the EmpoWomen CW.

Figure 2. EmpoWomen collaborative workspace

4.1.1 Collaborative project monitoring

To facilitate collaboration among partners, a collaborative [EmpoWomen Mastersheet](#) has been created. This document (spreadsheet format), accessible to all partners and in the root of the collaborative workspace, is the transposition of all relevant information from the GA (particularly the DoA) into an easy-to-access and editable document.

The [Mastersheet](#) is multi-tab document in which each tab includes specific information about the project:

- HOME: It is the table of contents of the document, where you can find quick access to all tabs of the document.
- Tabs: The document has different tabs.

- ✓ **WPs:** Contains basic information about the WPs, such as tasks, leaders for each task, contributors, duration, and the months corresponding to the project.
- ✓ **GANTT&meetings:** Includes the calendar of all project tasks, highlighting deliverable submission dates. It also provides a summary of consortium meetings with a direct link to the agenda and meeting minutes.
- ✓ **Deliverables and Milestones:** Provides a summary of all deliverables to be submitted throughout the project, including submission dates, the status of each deliverable (Not started, In Progress, Overdue, Done), the assigned member for review, and the status of that review. Project milestones and their status can also be found here.
- ✓ **KPIs:** Lists all project KPIs associated with objectives, impact, and C&D. Progress can be verified at months 6, 12, 18, and 24.
- ✓ **Risks:** This tab contains all project-associated risks, which will be monitored every 6 months, and their status will be reflected in this tab.
- ✓ **Action Points:** This tab reflects all action points resulting from meetings, including the responsible member, deadline, and status.
- ✓ **Open Calls:** Dedicated tab for the two open calls during the project, displaying the calendar, status, and documents for each.
- ✓ **Eligible Countries:** A reference tab listing the countries eligible for the open calls.
- ✓ **Events:** When a member identifies an event they will attend and shares information about the EmpoWomen project, evidence and information about the event should be documented here.
- ✓ **Partner Contact:** Contact information for all consortium members.
- ✓ **Associated Partners:** Contact information for all associated partners.

The Mastersheet is accessible to all members, but only the coordinator is authorized to edit it. Members have editing privileges for the "Deliverables and Milestones," "Action Points," and "Events" tabs as follows:

- ✓ **Deliverables and Milestones:** Partners assigned to produce a specific deliverable are obligated to report their progress and apprise the Project Coordinator (PC) of the deliverable's status. When the document is ready for review, the responsible partner must notify both the designated reviewer and the PC. Subsequently, upon completion of the review, the Deliverable Reviewer (DR) is required to inform both the deliverable manager and the PC. Additionally, the DR should keep the coordinator updated on the deliverable's progress and accurately document this information in the Mastersheet.
- ✓ **Action Points:** Those responsible for each action point should update its progress in this tab and inform both the coordinator and the involved partners.
- ✓ **Events:** All members must update their participation data in events related to the project.

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. is a screenshot of the EmpoWomen Mastersheet.

WP	No.	DELIV. TITLE	DELIV DESCRIPTION	LEAD PART	TYPE	DISS. LEVE	DELIV. DATE	SUBMISSION DATE	REVISION DATE	TEAM Folder	Status	Reviewer
WP 1	D1.1	Project Management Handbook	Internal guide stating the procedures and rules on project management (contacts, financial data, project KPIs, templates, guides) for project quality assurance.	SPLORO	R	PU	1	30/11/2023	15/11/2023 to 20/11/2023 (8:00 CET)	LINK	In Progress	All partners
	D1.2	Data Mgmt. Plan	Report on the use of data generated by the project following the open access to publications.	SPLORO	DMP	PU	3	30/01/2024			Not started	All partners
	D1.3	Monitoring report	Report containing information about the achievement of the qualitative and quantitative indicators set in the project.	SWG	R	CO	13	28/11/2024			Not started	TECHUA
	D1.3	Monitoring report	Report containing information about the achievement of the qualitative and quantitative indicators set in the project.	SWG	R	CO	24	30/10/2025			Not started	TECHUA
WP2	D2.1	Open call documentation	Information package needed to publish each of the open calls including guidelines, online form, leaflets, and open call announcement for distribution	SPLORO	R	PU	2	25/12/2023			In Progress	SWG
	D2.2	Discovery impact report	Documentation including relevant statistics and findings of the open calls. This will outline the actions taken, and outcomes achieved in relation to the promotional strategies during the first/second period of the project.	SPLORO	R	PU	8	27/06/2024			Not started	TECHUA
	D2.3	Beneficiaries' dataset	Open Dataset containing the list of beneficiaries of the open calls, project description and funds. Updates after the execution of each call.	SPLORO	DATA	PU	8	27/06/2024			Not started	SWG
	D2.1	Open call documentation	Information package needed to publish each of the open calls including guidelines, online form, leaflets, and open call announcement for distribution	SPLORO	R	PU	14	16/12/2024			Not started	SWG
	D2.2	Discovery impact report	Documentation including relevant statistics and findings of the open calls. This will outline the actions taken, and outcomes achieved in relation to the promotional strategies during the first/second period of the project.	SPLORO	R	PU	18	29/04/2025			Not started	TECHUA
	D2.3	Beneficiaries' dataset	Open Dataset containing the list of beneficiaries of the open calls, project description and funds. Updates after the execution of each call.	SPLORO	DATA	PU	18	29/04/2025			Not started	SWG
WP3	D3.1	Services Plan	Comprehensive list of services published in our website and as a booklet for consultation including the description of the services.	SWG	R	PU	6	29/04/2024			Not started	SPLORO
	D3.2	Impact Analysis	Report describing the execution and results from the accelerator. It will include the results of the feedback process and the analytical insights of the services.	SWG	R	PU	13	28/11/2024			Not started	SPLORO
	D3.1	Services Plan	Comprehensive list of services published in our website and as a booklet for consultation including the description of the services.	SWG	R	PU	18	29/04/2025			Not started	SPLORO
	D3.2	Impact Analysis	Report describing the execution and results from the accelerator. It will include the results of the feedback process and the analytical insights of the services.	SWG	R	PU	24	30/10/2025			Not started	SPLORO
WP4	D4.1	D&C plan	Dissemination, communication, and networking activities plan and guidelines for the project.	TECHUA	R	PU	2	25/12/2023			Not started	BAE
	D4.2	Report on D&C activities	Annual report on the activities performed in the project.	TECHUA	R	PU	13	28/11/2024			Not started	SPLORO
	D4.1	D&C plan	Dissemination, communication, and networking activities plan and guidelines for the project.	TECHUA	R	PU	14	16/12/2024			Not started	SPLORO
	D4.2	Report on D&C activities	Annual report on the activities performed in the project.	TECHUA	R	PU	24	30/10/2025			Not started	SPLORO
	D4.3	Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy	Report with the project results and how each partner and the consortium aim to exploit the project results in their business activities.	SPLORO	R	CO	24	30/10/2025			Not started	TECHUA

Figure 3. EmpoWomen Mastersheet – Deliverable control

4.2 Meetings and complementary communication

4.2.1 Representation in meetings

Any Member:

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;

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- and shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

4.2.2 Convening meetings.

The Coordinator shall convene ordinary meetings of the General Assembly at the beginning of the project (kick-off meeting at Month 1), project progress meetings at least once every six months (around Month 6, Month 12 and Month 18) and Final review at the end of the project (around Month 24).

In the case of general plenary meetings, to be organised every six months or as agreed by the General Assembly, preparation and organisation will follow the process agreed in the [CA](#). The locations and organizers of the consortium meetings every 6 months are reflected in Table 5.

Table 5. General Assembly meetings

Meeting	Month	Location
Pre-kick-off meeting	M1	online
First General Assembly meeting (KoM)	M1	Pamplona, Spain

The upcoming general assembly gathering is scheduled for March 2024 in Brussels, aligning with The Research and Innovations week. The venues for the M12, M18, and M24 meetings will be determined at a later date.

If necessary, extraordinary (additional ad-hoc) meetings of the General Assembly and/or virtual/physical technical meetings may be convened at any time upon written request of any Member in the case of an emergency situation.

4.2.3 Notice of a meeting

The Coordinator shall give written notice of a meeting to each Member as soon as possible and no later than 14 calendar days preceding an ordinary meeting and 7 calendar days preceding an extraordinary meeting. The notice of the meeting will include the venue where the meeting will take place (if physical) or the link to the online platform, the scheduled date, and the specified time of the meeting.

4.2.4 Agendas and meeting minutes.

To maximise the efficiency of organised meetings, agendas should always be set and communicated to all the partners involved. Particularly for general plenary meetings, the agenda should be sent at least 10 days before the meeting, or 7 calendar days before an extraordinary meeting.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member may add an item to the original agenda by written notice to all the other Members no later than 7 calendar days preceding the meeting.

During a meeting of the General Assembly the Members present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

Meetings of the General Assembly may also be held by tele- or videoconference or other telecommunication means.

The Coordinator shall produce minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. She shall send draft minutes via the consortium communication channels (i.e, email, slack, shared folders) to all Members within 15 calendar days of the meeting.

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 10 calendar days from receipt, no Party has sent an objection to the Coordinator with respect to the accuracy of the draft minutes by written notice.

If the leader of a Work Package (WP) coordinates a meeting related to their WP, they will be responsible for drafting the minutes.

The minutes will be available to all partners in the EmpoWomen Mastersheet on the tab called [GANTT&meetings](#).

4.2.5 Decisions without a meeting

Decisions on structural matters may also be made without a meeting if:

- a) the Coordinator circulates to all Members of the General Assembly a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least 10 calendar days after receipt by a Party and
- b) the decision is agreed by 2/3 of all Parties.

The Coordinator shall inform all the Members of the outcome of the vote.

A veto according to Section 3.2.7 of the CA may be submitted up to 15 calendar days after receipt of this information.

The decision will be binding after the Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

4.2.6 Voting rules and quorum

The General Assembly shall not deliberate and decide validly in meetings unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum).

If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the General Assembly shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more,

the Coordinator shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

Each Member present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.

A Party which the General Assembly has declared according to Section 4.2 (Consortium Agreement) to be a Defaulting Party may not vote.

Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.

4.2.7 Veto rights

A Party which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the General Assembly may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a Party may only veto such a decision during the meeting.

When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a Party may veto such decision during the meeting or within 15 calendar days after receipt of the draft minutes of the meeting.

When a decision has been taken without a meeting a Party may veto such decision within 15 calendar days after receipt of the written notice by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote.

In case of exercise of veto, the Parties shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all Parties.

A Party may neither veto decisions relating to its identification to be in breach of its obligations nor to its identification as a Defaulting Party. The Defaulting Party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or the consequences of them.

A Party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating the vote.

4.2.8 Communication channels

For everyday communication between project partners and for the organisation of online meetings, three main tools will be used by partners: Slack, Google Meets, Zoom and Microsoft Teams (incorporated as part of the Teams workspace). Teams is the main tool for online meetings involving all partners, including General Assembly meetings. Google Meets and Zoom can be used alternatively for any meeting organised within a shorter time frame (on-demand).

A Slack channel has been set up for the EmpoWomen project. Slack is a multi-function messaging system that will enable partners to communicate in a more *on demand* manner. Partners are encouraged to use Slack as a complementary tool to email for day-to-day communications, primarily for exchange of ideas and other discussions. Any discussion conducted via Slack that

leads to action points should be communicated via email to all parties involved, and those action points should be added to the mastersheet by the coordinator.

4.3 Email and mailing lists

Email is the primary means of day-to-day communication between the partners. To ensure selected information is known to all partners and respective representatives, a project mailing list has been set up. The mailing list used by the consortium is: EmpoWomen@sploro.eu.

This is an internal mailing list and only registered e-mails (managed by SPLORO) can send to or receive e-mails from the list.

Other mailing lists can be set up according to the specific needs of the project members. Any requests for additional mailing lists must be communicated to the PC.

5. Project reporting

This section describes the mandatory reporting processes and timings applicable to the EmpoWomen project. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**6 summarises the main reports that will have to be delivered by EmpoWomen and its partners (excluding deliverables). Further details on each report are provided in what follows.

Table 6. EmpoWomen project reporting

Report	Frequency	By whom	To whom
Internal reports	Every six (6) months	Prepared by each partner	PC
Final report	After completion of the project (M24)	PC with contributions from partners	EC
Cost statements (Form C)	End of reporting period (M24)	Prepared by each partner	EC
Timesheets	Monthly	Prepared by each partner	Partners keep on record

5.1 Internal reports and progress monitoring

Each partner must create and submit an internal report to the Project Coordinator (PC) every semester, detailing the activities undertaken during the respective semester. Partners are obligated to utilize the document provided by the PC for this purpose, which will be designed based on the format required by the European Commission for official reporting. This approach ensures optimal utilization of information during periodic and final reporting.

An initial draft of the internal report should be submitted within the first 15 days following the conclusion of the semester. This allows for an internal review by the PC within 5 days, with an additional 5-day window for partners to provide any necessary updates. The expectation is that the internal reports will be finalized by the end of the month, specifically within 30 days after the semester concludes.

The internal reports will also focus on the financial performance of each partner during the preceding semester. The Financial Manager of the Coordination team will furnish partners with instructions and relevant templates towards the semester's end.

In light of these aspects, it is crucial to incorporate financial details in the reports to track whether a partner is exceeding or falling short of the budget. Furthermore, clarify that the project monitoring process covers technical advancements, outcomes, deliverables, adherence to the Work Package (WP), and the continuous evaluation and updating of any identified risks.

If a partner is overspending or underspending, the steps or procedures to address the situation effectively are explained in Section 5.2.

5.2 Excess payments

A Party has received excess payment

- a) if the payment received from the Coordinator exceeds the amount declared or
- b) if a Party has received payments but, within the last year of the Project, its real Project costs fall significantly behind the costs it would be entitled to according to the Consortium Plan.

In case a Party has received excess payment, the Party has to inform the Coordinator and return the relevant amount to the Coordinator without undue delay. In case no refund takes place within 30 days upon request for return of excess payment from the Coordinator, the Party is in substantial breach of the Consortium Agreement.

Amounts which are not refunded by a breaching Party and which are not due to the Granting Authority, shall be apportioned by the Coordinator to the remaining Parties pro rata according to their share of total costs of the Project as identified in the Consortium Budget, until recovery from the breaching Party is possible.

5.3 Final Report for the EC.

As defined in Article 21 of the GA, the project must report to the European Commission. Regarding periodic reports, these must be submitted to the European Commission within 60 days following the end of each reporting period. EmpoWomen only has one reporting period at the end of the project, in month 24.

The **Final report** consists of:

- A **Technical Report**: includes an overview of the action implementation. It must be prepared using the template available in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool.
- The **Financial part** of the final report includes:

- the financial statements (individual and consolidated; for all beneficiaries/affiliated entities)
- the explanation on the use of resources (or detailed cost reporting table, if required)
- the certificates on the financial statements (CFS)

The financial statements must detail the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action.

Information on the submission of periodic reports can be accessed at the following [link](#).

5.4 Timesheets

In accordance with standard EU practices, project partners must maintain monthly project time records (i.e., timesheets) detailing their day-to-day project-related activities for each month. These records should adhere to any existing standards set by the Partner. It is the responsibility of the Partners to keep copies of the time records signed and countersigned by the supervisor, as they may be necessary for auditing purposes.

6. Project Processes

6.1 Risk Management

All projects are subject to foreseeable and unforeseeable risks. Risk management addresses those risks that could jeopardise the project meeting its objectives and deliver the planned results.

Within EmpoWomen, the identification of risks is bi-directional: top-down and bottom-up. In the top-down approach, it is the PC who is responsible for checking potential risks during plenary meetings or other scheduled meetings. In the bottom-up approach, it is the Task and WP leaders that must identify risks and inform the PC about them.

Risks are evaluated according to two main criteria: the probability a risk might happen (“likelihood”) and the impact it has in case it occurs (“severity”). At the proposal stage and later during the Grant Agreement preparation, 10 risks were identified. The likelihood and severity of these 10 risks was classified using a scale of “low”, “medium”, “high”.

All project risks are incorporated into the EmpoWomen Mastersheet, ensuring that all partners are informed about the pre-defined risks. Regular reviews will be conducted to assess their status. Irrespective of the method used to recognize the risks (whether top-down or bottom-up), the consortium collaboratively works to detect emerging risks at the earliest stage possible and determine the most effective mitigation approach.

During these assessments, and as the project progresses, the classification of each risk may be changed. Any change that is an increase in the likelihood or severity of a risk will lead to the development of clear risk mitigation plan. The plan must be developed by the Task and WP leader to which the risk is associated and communicated to the General Assembly. Risk mitigation plans may include alternative courses of action, possible workarounds, a timeline for risk handling activities, implications on the consortium partners, and one or more recommended courses of action.

After a risk mitigation plan is initiated, the risk and agreed courses of action will continue to be monitored by the involved partners.

6.2 Issue Management

Having a good working relationship among the project team members will be a prerequisite for a quick resolution of problems and issues. The partners shall always try to reach an agreement on conflicts. However, if this is not possible, the resolution of problems and conflicts must be handled systematically.

Conflicts will be solved at the lowest level possible. If an agreement cannot be reached at a task or WP level, then the Project Coordinator will mediate. If that is not satisfactory, then the General

Assembly will take a decision, and if necessary, it will ask for the authorisation of the European Commission.

Definitive conflict resolution procedures are laid down in the Consortium Agreement. This document formalizes the rights, obligations, relationships and procedures within the consortium, as well as any other relevant issues such as the use of background material, etc. In case of conflict between participants on access rights, the coordinator should advise the General Assembly for arbitration (in correlation with EC rules).

6.3 Quality assurance

This section addresses the quality assurance procedures of the EmpoWomen project. The establishment of quality procedures aims to ensure a high quality of project deliverables and project management.

While the PC has the overall responsibility for ensuring quality assurance, all partners are responsible for ensuring the highest quality in the work they deliver (e.g., complying with templates or keeping deadlines). Therefore, quality assurance is the joint responsibility of all partners and will be applied at various levels of the project's activities.

6.3.1 Quality assurance process for documents (deliverables and presentations)

During the EmpoWomen lifetime, several documents (particularly project deliverables but also presentations) will be developed. A set of rules must be followed to ensure these are developed with quality and that, regardless of their main content, they share a common structure. To ensure this, templates have been developed, which are available on the collaborative workspace, specifically in the folder dedicated to WP4.

When using the templates, several aspects should be taken into consideration, as discussed in the sub-sections below.

6.3.2 Document standards and guidelines

Document languages

With exception to specific documents that are required for local activities, all documents must be developed in the **English language (UK English)**.

Document owners and contributors

Each deliverable has a designated lead partner, which in principle will correspond to the document owner. The owner is the main responsible to produce the deliverable, to make a proposal of a table of contents, and to manage the collection of inputs from other partners.

Partners should consult the GA or the EmpoWomen Mastersheet to identify the deliverables they own or for which they are expected to be reviewers. For documents where contributors may be required, the document owner is encouraged to take advantage of the document collaboration

tools. This will minimise the circulation of documentation via e-mail and ensure better management and tracking of input from contributors.

6.3.3 Document development and review

To ensure relevant, rigorous, high quality, and the timely development of project deliverables, these will be internally reviewed by partners following a defined procedure.

All deliverables have a designated responsible (DR), which is clearly outlined in the DoA as well as in the shared Mastersheet. All deliverables have also been, at this stage, allocated an internal reviewer. This is a partner that is not directly involved in the deliverable development (and associated Task) and with some degree of technical knowledge to ensure an adequate review. Any reviewer with any conflict must inform the PC so that an alternative is identified.

The following process will apply to developing and reviewing deliverables:

- **Table of Contents – 60 days before due date:** The DR (and deliverable reviewer) define and agree on the Table of Contents, sharing it with all relevant partners. The WPL and PC can suggest that it is shared to the consortium for further input.
- **Alpha version – 45 days before due date:** Is a first draft to collect contributions and is sent to all contributors and the WPL.
- **Beta version – 20 days before due date:** Is a final draft version to be sent to the internal reviewer, WPL and PC.
- The internal review should be provided within 15 days before the deliverable due date, accompanied by the review form (available in the workspace).
- **Final version – 5 days before due date:** Is the final version, reflecting the updates as provided during the review.
 - **The PC submits the deliverable in PDF format to the EC.**

Any delays identified by the DR should be immediately communicated to the partners involved. Any delay that affects the submission of the deliverable to the EC by the defined date must be notified to the PC at least 30 days in advance so that the Project Officer is informed. A reasonable justification on the delay must be prepared by the DR and provided to the PC.

6.3.4 Deliverable acceptance

In principle, deliverables are only formally accepted after the official reporting period (scheduled for M24). Deliverables that are not accepted by the EC will require a specific set of revisions that will be defined by the EC's experts. Any request for revision of deliverables (or other reports) will result in additional work by the partners and could delay payments associated to the reporting period.

Therefore, it is in the interest of the partners that all documents are developed in a timely manner and with the expected quality.

6.4 Dissemination and communication processes

Dissemination and communication efforts are essential for the success of EmpoWomen by promoting the project’s objectives, activities, and achievements. Given its relevance, every partner in the consortium has a dedicated effort in this Work Package (WP4 – Ecosystem building and exploitation).

All partners share responsibilities regarding communication and dissemination activities and thus, there are some directives to follow so that we can:

- Report our effort and results to the European Commission.
- Reach the KPIs as described in the DoA.

As a first step, all partners should read and be familiar with the Communication and Dissemination Plans drafted in the D.4.1 D&C Plan. Deliverable 4.1 is to be produced in M2 and M14 of the project and details all the actions to be implemented in this regard and their objectives.

To measure the level of attainment of those objectives, a list of KPIs for Communication & Dissemination is presented below:

Table 7. EmpoWomen Communication & Dissemination KPI

DISSEMINATION	Description	Target
Project website	No. of unique visitors (monthly average)	(+300)
Social Media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	(+2000)
	Total reach (impressions by the end of the project)	(+12000)
Publications	Clipping/publications coverage	(+30)
Press Releases	No. of newsletters contributed/released	(+6)
Podcasts	No. of tech talks (female founder’s podcasts) created	(+20)
Printed material	No. of hard copies (i.e., flyers) distributed	(+2500)
COMMUNICATION	Description	Target

Investors Matchmaking	No. of matchmaking events organised	4
Webinars	No. of webinars organised	(+30)
Heroines Stories	No. success stories generated and promoted (end of the project)	18
Events	No. of self-organised events	(+10)
	No. of external events we expect to participate	5

To fulfil these obligations, and to keep track of all efforts, EmpoWomen will have internal tools, as addressed in the sections below:

6.5 Communication & Dissemination tracker

Communication & Dissemination are a collective effort that all partners need and should contribute to. Whenever a partner performs a communication or dissemination action/activity, it needs to be reported, otherwise, traceability is lost. For this reason, we have created a simple Communication & Dissemination tracker to list and report all efforts linked to the communication and dissemination of the project and its results, where all partners should provide their input on potential opportunities.

In this tracker, you will find tabs such as:

- Newsletters:** The consortium foresees the production of semi-annual digital newsletters during the project, whose purpose will be to raise awareness of the project and its latest news. For ensuring national dissemination and impact, the Newsletters will be translated into the partners' languages, moreover, each national Newsletter could be customised with particular articles, news, or events relevant at the national level. These newsletters will be sent proactively to the database of stakeholders to be built during the project, and it will also be possible for interested parties to subscribe via the web platform.
- Events** - Whenever there is an opportunity for a virtual or physical event in which to promote the project or any of our activities, please contact TECHUA directly to plan the promotional materials / online channel content for the event. Partners should fill in the Events tabs in the C&D database (EmpoWomen mastersheet) with those upcoming / relevant to the project.

- **Webinars:** Within the comprehensive dissemination strategy for EmpoWomen, webinars play a pivotal role in achieving widespread visibility, fostering awareness about the project, and engaging stakeholders in its activities.
- **Publications:** In line with the extensive dissemination strategy for EmpoWomen, the publication component serves as a crucial avenue for sharing information, insights, and project updates.
- **Social media** (to count impressions): The official social network pages of the project will be launched on Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn. Following the definition of the content plan in collaboration with the general assembly, efforts will be intensified to increase the frequency of publications. The shared content will encompass project updates, information on open calls, profiles of selected startups and entrepreneurs, fact sheets and brochures, details about events, project results, and pertinent insights extracted from public deliverables.
- **Matchmaking events:** In the EmpoWomen project, the Matchmaking Events section plays a crucial role in fostering connections and collaboration. The primary objectives include organizing targeted events to facilitate meaningful interactions between stakeholders, startups, and entrepreneurs.

This will be a living document for the whole project duration, available to all partners in the Shared Teams at EmpoWomen - Consortium Shared Repository > WP4, as well as embedded into the EmpoWomen Mastersheet.

Partners are required to fill in the name and person in charge and the status of the activity (Opportunity, Confirmed, Cancelled, Done) in the tracker to follow up effectively on every action.

Further tabs can be added to this document according to the needs of the project.

6.6 Editorial Calendar

The project will publish and share articles about its milestones, progress, and findings through the website, blogs, social media, or any other relevant platforms. These articles are to be produced by project partners and signed either as "EmpoWomen Consortium", "EmpoWomen" or listing specific people as authors. Typically, these articles have an extension of no more than one page and include a heading, main text, photos and/or graphical elements.

To plan out in a coordinated way the necessary content for these pieces, an editorial calendar was created. The Editorial is a living document for the whole project duration and is available to all partners in the Shared TEAMS at EmpoWomen - Consortium Shared Repository > WP4, as well as embedded into the EmpoWomen Mastersheet.

TECHUA will support the partners with the proposal of articles/authors as the project progresses, follow up with partners on their progress, select the platform for publication (unless there is one agreed upon by the consortium), and keep track of all external mentions.

6.7 Stakeholders database

As outlined in the DoA, the dissemination of EmpoWomen messages is crucial to reach a substantial number of contact points through email campaigns/direct messaging. To facilitate this, an internal stakeholder database will be created. This serves as a potent strategy for promoting activities and results, as well as garnering support for open calls. Email campaigns play a crucial role in connecting with various entities, fostering engagement with partnerships and networks.

TECHUA will design and execute a portfolio of templates to fit each specific target group, integrating call-to-action measures to increase traffic. The project will use EU GDPR-compliant solutions.

The creation of this database will be coordinated with the efforts made in this sense in the framework of WP4, especially Task 4.1 Marketing Strategy and Initial Set Up.

This Stakeholders database will be available to all partners in the Shared TEAMS at EmpoWomen - Consortium Shared Repository > WP4, as well as embedded into the EmpoWomen Mastersheet for easier access.

Important! To share your communication and outreach updates, address any questions, make suggestions, or request support, please contact TECHUA at tatiana@techukraine.org.

7. Project closing

The EmpoWomen project has a total duration of 24-months, with a scheduled end date of 31st of October 2025. At that stage, there will still be several activities, formal and informal, to be carried out.

7.1 Final acceptance and formal project closure

The project is only formally closed and accepted once the final reports, including costs, are formally approved by the EC, which will likely happen beyond the 60-day reporting period.

7.2 Reflection on the project

After completing the assigned tasks within the framework of the EmpoWomen project, all participants are encouraged to take a step back and reflect on the work accomplished, both at an individual level and within the context of their organizations and the project itself.

When considering this reflection, it would be valuable to open a document and create a detailed summary of all the work undertaken. The impact achieved can be analyzed, not only on a personal level but also within the organization and the broader community. Questions to ponder include: What actions did I take that had a significant impact? What lessons did I learn during this process? To what extent is society benefiting today from the work carried out in the EmpoWomen project? Additionally, it is crucial to think about how to effectively support the sustainability of the work accomplished.

Lessons learned, identified best practices, and recommendations applicable to future activities within the EmpoWomen framework should be identified. This will contribute not only to the ongoing development of the project but also to the strengthening of future initiatives, ensuring a positive and sustainable impact in the promotion of women's entrepreneurship in advanced technologies.

7.3 Document and result archiving

Although the project has come to an end, keep in mind that the project and/or partners may still be subject to an external audit. For that purpose, it is important to ensure that all documents and evidence related to the implementation of the project are well organised.

Follow your internal documentation and information management procedures, but ensure you keep copies/ have access to:

- Project deliverables, particularly those you've authored and/or contributed to.
- Official periodic/ final report.
- All evidence related to costs incurred in the project.

7.4 Celebrate our success!

Once the EC notifies the consortium of the approval of all project reports and costs, we can finally celebrate! At this point, we will know that we have delivered results within the expectations of the EC and that we have delivered a project that has made an impact in the different domains the project addresses.

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8. Final considerations

This deliverable is the Project Management Handbook, a document that aims to support all EmpoWomen partners in their day-to-day activities and the delivery of the project.

The handbook complements the GA and CA, which have been signed by the partners, and are hierarchically above the handbook in terms of rules to consider in project management.

The handbook is a living document that may be updated over the course of the project to cover additional aspects of relevance to all partners.

